

Project	GUTTA
Work Package number	1
Work Package title	Project management and coordination of activities
Deliverable number	1.3.3.
Deliverable title	Steering Committee meeting report #3
Deliverable Responsible Partner	CMCC
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Deliverable due date	2022-05-31
Deliverable latest review date	2021-11-26
Comments	Web-meeting due to the COVID-19 pandemic

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0. Executive Summary

The fourth GUTTA Steering Committee meeting (SCm4) took place on November 17, 2021. However, due to persisting emergency caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, it was held in online mode only.

The SCm4 consisted of two sessions, with the first one more focusing on the results achieved so far, and the latter on the steps to be carried out till the project final events. The technical, financial, and communication aspects of the project were considered.

The SC number in the title of this deliverable does not account for the fact that a SC meeting was held in April 2021 for discussing the Major Change to the GUTTA project.

For the shortcuts employed in this report, we refer to the official GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at <https://zenodo.org/record/5713897>.

1. Report of the meeting

The fourth meeting of the GUTTA Steering Committee (SCm4) is here documented by means of its agenda, list of participants, main outcomes, and online published contents.

1.1 Agenda

The SCm4 took place on November 17, 2021, following the agenda below:

Session A	Recap on work done in RP5-6
9:00	Welcome, overview of SCm4, and group screenshot <i>Paola Agostini (CMCC)</i>
9:15	Feedback collection activities <i>Maria Mihalić (CSA)</i>
9:30	AdSP progress since SCm3 <i>Evangelia Piteni (AdSP)</i>
9:45	MMPI and UNIRI activities <i>Tomislav Budić (MMPI)</i>
10:00	COVID-19 and mobility data in Croatia, via the eRG framework <i>Corentin Cot (CNRS)</i>
10:15	Unizd's progress since SCm3 <i>Josip Orović (Unizd)</i>
10:30	GUTTA-VISIR: frontend application <i>Saloni Kyal (CMCC)</i>
10:45	Group discussion on session A's presentations <i>All</i>
11:00	break
Session B	Planning GUTTA's conclusion
11:15	Next technical steps <i>Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)</i>
11:35	Next Communication steps <i>Laura Caciagli (CMCC)</i>
11:55	Next administrative steps <i>Paola Agostini (CMCC)</i>
12:15	Interactive session on www.GUTTA-VISIR.eu
12:30	Group discussion on session B's presentations <i>All</i>

1.2 Participants

A total of 16 people took part to the zoom meeting, as documented in both Fig.1 and Tab.2. Evangelia Piteni joined the meeting via smartphone and was not connected at the time the screenshot was taken. In total, people connected to SCm4 from six different Countries, and across 5.5 time zones. The gender distribution was: 6 females, 10 males.

Figure 1 Group screenshot.

Table 1 List of participants

No.	Surname	Name	Organization	Location
1	Agostini	Paola	CMCC	Italy
2	Cacciapaglia	Giacomo	CNRS	France
3	Caciagli	Laura	CMCC	Italy
4	Carelli	Lorenzo	CMCC	Italy
5	Cot	Corentin	CNRS	Switzerland
6	Deželjin	Davor	MMPI	Croatia
7	Kyal	Saloni	CMCC	India
8	Madeira	Miguel	EMSA	Portugal
9	Mannarini	Gianandrea	CMCC	Italy

10	Mihalić	Maria	CSA	Croatia
11	Orović	Josip	UniZd	Croatia
12	Piteni	Evangelia	AdSP	Italy
13	Salhi	Amal	CMCC	Italy
14	Salinas	Mario	CMCC	Italy
15	Scuro	Matteo	CMCC	Italy
16	Zrilić	Martin	UniZd	Croatia

1.3. Main outcomes

The outcomes are presented in reference to the specific sessions in Sect.1.3.1. and 1.3.2.

1.3.1 Session A

Piteni

She informed that a FLC for AdSP has finally been appointed. Nevertheless, it was not possible to verify the expenditures of RP5 in due course.

Also, the procedure for procuring an external expertise (EE) is still ongoing. This resource is supposed to oversee the tasks for the accomplishment of D.5.1.2.

Mihalić

She made the point about CSA severe understaffing with respect to the GUTTA project because both Mrs. Vukelić-Čemeljić and Mr. Vidas left the Association during last year.

In reference to the process of amendment of the EU-MRV regulation, Mrs. Jutta Paulus of the EU Parliament was contacted. She informed CSA about the stall of that process.

Dzeljin

He informed the partnership that the work for the preparation of the HR final event (FE) of GUTTA has started. The event will likely take place in Rijeka. Its date will be finalized shortly after SCm4. Furthermore, an EE has been appointed by MMPI to the University of Rijeka, Faculty of Faculty of Maritime Studies. After SCm4, a colleague of MMPI (Budić) will inform the partnership if the financial absorption from the EE is occurring according to the time schedule.

Cot

He presented the results to date from application of the eRG framework (Cacciapaglia et al, 2020¹) to the COVID-19 diffusion in Croatia. The study was motivated by the question “did maritime passenger transport contributed to the second wave² of COVID-19 in Croatia?” In order to answer

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-020-72611-5>

² August-September 2020

it, mobility data from various sources were collected: CIMIS ferry passenger data, terrestrial mobility on both highways and railways (provided by the University of Rijeka in its capacity of subcontractor of MMPI), flight data. The epidemiological record from NUTS-2 regions of Croatia was well captured by the eRG framework, but for the Zagreb region. Here, further developments are needed. However, the provisional conclusion is that here is no evidence that ferry passenger traffic triggered the second wave in Croatia.

Orović

He presented the contribution by UniZd to the dissemination of information regarding the outcomes of the GUTTA project on occasion of several national and international conferences (including: 14th Baška GNSS Conference, SMATECH, EU CONEXUS meeting) he attended during the last few months, also in quality of invited speaker.

Kyal

She made a thorough description of the structure of the GUTTA-VISIR (GV) web application³. The presentation covered the various sections of GV (Home, About, Help, Feedback, Help) and the various products accessible through it (individual routes, bundles, linecharts, diagrams of CO₂ relative savings, route exportation). An example from GV is provided in Fig.2. A detailed description of the system, from its back- to its frontend, is deferred to GUTTA deliverable D. 4.4.1.

Discussion

After each presentation or during the discussion slot at the end of Session A, several remarks and questions were risen. In particular:

- Madeira: He commented that some of the items proposed with the EU-MRV amendment procedure are likely to be considered through other legislative initiatives, such as the fitfor55package. In particular, the inclusion of also GHGs other than CO₂ is likely to become mandatory. Also, the cap on emission could occur through inclusion of shipping into the EU-ETS, which at present seems likely.
- Cacciapaglia: He recommended to perform a statistical investigation concerning the CO₂ savings computed by GV during a longer timeframe;
- Mannarini made several points:
 - It is important to appreciate the non-trivial route diversions computed by GV in presence of significant meteo-marine conditions (e.g. high sea states). These are also the situations in which the tool would compute the largest CO₂ savings. While it can happen that the optimal routes are identical to the least-distance ones, these are not the most useful ones to be used for conveying the added value of GV;

³ <https://www.gutta-visir.eu/>

- He emphasized the need for collecting feedback on GV in the short term, i.e. in the next few weeks after SCm4. This is due to the fact that a minimum time of about two months is required for designing, planning, implementing, and testing any significant change to GV, and they should possibly be finalized before the HR-FE of March 2022;
- GV include both static information relative to ship simulator of UniZd (used once for generating a look-up-table of the ferry performance in waves) and dynamic, information relative to the optimal routes, based on daily updated information regarding the sea current and wave forecast fields. See Fig.3 for more details.

Figure 2 Example of the dashboard of the GUTTA-VISIR web application. More detail in Saloni Kyal's presentation available at the link provided in Sect. 1.4.

Figure 3 Basic steps behind the GV application: 1) a real ferry; 2) its representation at the UniZd ship simulator installed at Zadar; 3) its seakeeping and performance look-up-table (LUT), derived from data collected once at 2); 4) the VISIR-2 model, making use of metocean forecast fields from CMES and the LUT from 3); 5) the backend infrastructure at the CMCC HPC in Lecce, active operationally twice a day; 6) the web app www.gutta-visir.eu enabling the enduser to browse operational least-CO₂ ferry routes on his/her device.

1.3.2 Session B

This session comprised three presentations to recap the status of GUTTA and next steps, from various perspectives (technical, communication, finance) as well as two brief interactive sessions and some time for discussion.

Mannarini

He first reviewed the main achievements of GUTTA during its first 35 months. They were distributed according to the three specific objectives of the project. In the second part of his presentation, he focused on what is left to be done till project's end, highlighting timing and PP responsibilities in achieving it. The FE in Italy was announced to be on May 4-5, 2022, in Lecce.

Caciagli

As Communication Officer of GUTTA, she reviewed the activity performed by the various PPs in disseminating the results of the project through social media, institutional PPs' websites, GUTTA webpage, organizing webinars and other online events, or realizing other outreach activities, such

as the brochures and the in-person events so far. She stressed the importance of contributing to the project video, which production is going to start in the coming few weeks.

Agostini

She first recalled the major change (MC) the consortium got approved last May, with its main consequences on activities, timing, and budget breakdown.

She then reported about the financial absorption of GUTTA per WP and budget lines. There is presently an underspending in WP4 which is mainly caused by missing expenditures for EE. This is likely to be partly recovered thanks to MMPI's EE in RP5, but absorption by AdSP is still null. The total gap in expenditure currently amounts to over 22 kEUR. There are still numerous deliverables to be prepared till project's end. Finally, she shared with the partnership the concern expressed by the GUTTA's PO (Mr. Rottoni) who expressively requested GUTTA to spend as much as planned and to avoid any further underspending.

Interactive sessions

This part included a test of the mentimeter⁴ platform and a demo of GV.

- Mentimeter or any similar tool might help raising active participation by the attendees of the GUTTA FEs. The tool was tested with the two questions provided in Fig.4 and, despite the relative small number of participants, it confirmed its potential to generate emotional involvement and raising the level of attention and awareness.
- The live demo of GV was carried out by Mannarini, who guided the participants through the various functionalities of the web application.

⁴ <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

a)

b)

Figure 4 Mentimeter poll results to the questions a) “Write one work to define the GUTTA project” and b) “Where do we need to be more focussed before the project ends?”.

Discussion

During Session B, several remarks and questions were risen. In particular:

- Madeira made the point that the information regarding the gross tonnage (GT) of the ferry used in the simulator should be provided on the GV help page for easing comparisons with other vessels;
- Mannarini suggested to check together with the PO is there is a minimum value for the relative financial absorption of a IT-HR Interreg project, as we are currently heading towards a non-negligible underspending.

1.4 Online resources

Presentations of both Sessions of SCm4 can be downloaded from the following URL:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1cUU8nX_1-Lce_5nsfxR1VnOjCGt5ldZt?usp=sharing

2. Conclusions

GUTTA SCm4 was a compact and productive event, with a quite good participation by PP delegates through a virtual meeting tool.

This was supposed to be the last SC meeting before the final GUTTA conference in HR. The urgency of setting a precise date for the event in Croatia was stressed during SCm4.

Currently, the largest criticality of the project regards underspending by some PPs, for which clarifications and action should be taken during the current RP5, to mitigate any possible shortcoming for both the partnership and the IT-HR Interreg programme.

However, GUTTA delivered the GV system (www.gutta-visir.eu), an innovative tool with the potential to contribute to greening of CB ferry connections between Italy and Croatia. It is necessary to become confident with it, before engaging in dissemination. Also, all PPs should engage in both the production of the final project video and collection of feedback on GV for making it closer to the expectations of the stakeholders.

GV is the most direct contribution of GUTTA to the 4.1O1 output indicator “Improved multimodal transport services” of the programme.